

Synthesis of 3-(Substituted Benzyl)-5-alkyl Rhodanines

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Preparation of benzylamines, and benzylammonium dithiocarbamates (not isolated) and their condensation with α -halo-fatty acids were carried out according to Raval and Trivedi¹. Rhodanines were obtained in 50% yield and were crystallised from ethanol. Compounds prepared are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Compounds. (R=)	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.		No.	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.				Found.	Reqd.
I. R' = Me.										
1	<i>o</i> -Cl	109°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ONClS ₂	23.8	23.7	13	68°	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ ONClS ₂	22.6	22.4
2	<i>p</i> -Cl	107°	"	23.9	23.7	14	64°	"	22.5	22.4
3	<i>o</i> -Me	101°	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ONS ₂	25.7	25.5	15	72°	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ ONS ₂	24.5	24.2
4	<i>m</i> -Me	104°	"	25.6	25.5	16	75°	"	24.4	24.2
5	<i>p</i> -Me	107°	"	25.8	25.5	17	79°	"	24.3	24.2
6	<i>o</i> -Br	111°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ONBrS ₂	20.4	20.3	18	89°	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ ONBrS ₂	19.6	19.4
7	<i>p</i> -Br	116°	"	20.5	20.3	19	95°	"	19.5	19.4
8	3,4-DiMe	100°	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ ONS ₂	24.3	24.2	20	71°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ ONS ₂	23.1	22.9
9	2,4-DiMe	103°	"	24.4	24.2	21	64°	"	23.0	22.9
10	2,5-DiMe	101°	"	24.4	24.2	22	59°	"	23.2	22.9
11	2,4-(Cl) ₂	69°	C ₁₁ H ₉ ONCl ₂ S ₂	21.2	21.0	23	86°	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ONCl ₂ S ₂	20.2	20.0
12	3,4-(Cl) ₂	83°	"	21.1	21.0	24	60°	"	20.1	20.0
II. R' = Et.										
III. R' = <i>n</i> -Pr.										
25	<i>o</i> -Cl	60°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ ONClS ₂	21.6	21.4				20.6	20.4
26	<i>p</i> -Cl	52°	"	21.5	21.4	37	56°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ ONClS ₂	22.0	21.6
27	<i>o</i> -Me	81°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ ONS ₂	23.0	22.9	38	65°	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ ONS ₂	23.1	21.8
28	<i>m</i> -Me	78°	"	23.2	22.9	39	60°	"	21.9	21.8
29	<i>p</i> -Me	72°	"	23.1	22.9	40	73°	"	18.1	17.9
30	<i>o</i> -Br	80°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ ONBrS ₂	18.9	18.6	41	80°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ ONBrS ₂	19.2	17.9
31	<i>p</i> -Br	86°	"	18.7	18.6	42	87°	"	23.6	23.3
32	3,4-DiMe	61°	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ ONS ₂	21.9	21.8	43	71°	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ ONS ₂	23.4	23.3
33	2,4- "	68°	"	22.0	21.8	44	69°	"	23.5	23.3
34	2,5- "	70°	"	22.0	21.8	45	77°	"	18.6	18.4
35	2,4-(Cl) ₂	59°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ ONCl ₂ S ₂	19.4	19.2	46	61°	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ ONCl ₂ S ₂	18.5	18.4
36	3,4-(Cl) ₂	80°	"	19.3	19.2	47	91°	"		

1. *This Journal*, 1962, 39, 53.

In a preliminary screening, compounds No. 2,9,10, 12, 13, 14, 22, 23, 24, 26, 35 and 36 did not reveal significant activity when tested against, *Staph. aureus* (gram positive), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (gram negative), *Trichomonas foetus* (protozoan), *Candida albicans* (fungus) and *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (fungus)

Thanks of the authors are due to the Ahmedabad Education Society for facilities and to the State Industrial Research Committee, the Government of Gujarat, for a research grant to one of them (J. J. T.). They are grateful to Dr. Maxwell Gordon and Smith Kline and French Laboratories U. S. A. for antimicrobial screening of the compounds.

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Received August 10, 1964.